

A Study of Attitude towards Classroom Teaching of Secondary School Teachers in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

This study conveyed the status of attitude towards classroom teaching of the secondary school teachers. The study bears the full angle of the quantitative research phenomena. The main objective of the study was to compare the Attitude towards their classroom teaching of secondary school teachers among categorical variables like Gender (Male-Female), Locale (Rural-Urban) & Training (Trained-Untrained). The study employed a survey design in which surveys were conducted to collect the data from the respondent teachers. 382 secondary school teachers were selected by random sampling. To measure the attitude of the secondary school teachers towards classroom teaching, Attitude towards Classroom Teaching Scale (ACTS), by the researcher and Dr. Guha (2017) was used in the study. The collected data was normally distributed and thus parametric statistics was used confidently for data analysis. Both Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used to reach the analysis and interpretation. Significant difference was observed between trained and untrained teachers but no significant differences were reported between male and female teachers and rural and urban teachers respectively.

Keywords: Attitude towards classroom teaching, Secondary school teachers

INTRODUCTION

In modern world, attitudes of people are considered more important than their experiences and academic preparation. In that sense a positive attitude towards classroom teaching is a key to success and progress in the knowledge based societies. A good teacher is like a candle which consumes itself to light the way for others. The pivotal position of teacher in an educational system, in particular and in nation building, in general, is of tremendous importance. The quality and performance of teachers are always considered as determining factors for the success of educational changes. The quality of teachers largely depends upon their personal acumen and the quality of their professional preparation as teachers (Duggal, 2005, p. 3). Another important factor that affects a teacher's success and efficiency is his/her attitude towards classroom teaching. It is obvious that the quality of teaching force is not governed only by the qualification, pedagogical knowledge and teaching skill of teachers, but also their attitude, enthusiasm, dedication and commitment in teaching.

Ahluwalia (1978) undertook a study on the development of a teacher attitude inventory and a study of change in professional attitude of prospective teachers. Following were the conclusions of the study: (i) The mean attitude scores were found to decrease rather than increasing at the end of the training programme, (ii) Sex wise and institution wise mean attitude score differences were

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found but these were not significant, (iii) Sex was not found to be either a determinant or differential of change in professional attitude of prospective teacher as a consequence of teacher's preparation programmes.

Naidu (1978) made a study on attitude of male and female teachers towards teaching. The study was based on sample of 360 teachers of Andhra Pradesh. The study revealed that all teachers have a favorable attitude towards teaching but female teachers have a more favorable attitude towards teaching than male teachers.

Mann (1980) conducted a study on "Some correlates of success in teaching of secondary school teachers." The tools employed were 16PF test and teacher attitude inventory. The findings of the study were as follows: (1) the relationship between attitude of teachers towards the teaching profession, classroom teaching and success in teaching was significant. (2) The successful teachers had healthier attitude towards teaching profession than the unsuccessful teachers. (3) Teaching experience was not related to success in teaching and (4) there was significant difference in personality characteristics, attitudes towards teaching profession of successful and unsuccessful teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare the attitude towards classroom teaching between male and female secondary school teachers.
2. To compare the attitude towards classroom teaching between rural and urban secondary school teachers.
3. To compare the attitude towards classroom teaching between trained and untrained secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES

H_0 : There would be no significant difference between male secondary school teachers and female secondary school teachers in their attitude towards classroom teaching.

H_{02} : There would be no significant difference between rural secondary school teachers and urban secondary school teachers in their attitude towards classroom teaching.

H_{03} : There would be no significant difference between trained secondary school teachers and untrained secondary school teachers in their attitude towards classroom teaching.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The quantitative approach was used by the present researcher as it was the most appropriate design for this research. The investigation was reductionist in nature. The study employed a survey design also in which surveys were conducted by the present researcher personally to collect all the data from the respondent teachers.

Variables

Major variables – Attitude towards classroom teaching

Categorical variables – Gender (Male-Female), Locale (Rural-Urban) and Training (Trained-Untrained)

Population & Sample

The population of the study was all secondary school teachers of West Bengal, teaching in the secondary schools under control of West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE). Out of 23 districts of West Bengal, 13 districts were selected randomly and from those 13 districts 72 secondary schools were selected randomly and from those 72 secondary schools, 7 teachers were selected randomly from each of the school.

Tools

To measure Attitude of the secondary school teachers towards classroom teaching, the standardized scale developed by the researchers and Dr. Guha (2017) was used named 'Attitude towards Classroom Teaching (ACTS)'. That inventory was a 37 item Likert instrument consisting five alternatives. The respondent had to tick (√) any one alternative among five alternatives.

Scoring Procedure

For the scale, Likert continuum - strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree had been provided to each item. Each item alternative was assigned a weight ranging from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree) for favorable items and in the case of unfavorable items the range of weight was reversed *i.e.* from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

PRESENTATION OF DATA

The presentation of data, collected by the present researcher was done in order to make inferences and generalizations about the population. After that data were tabulated and descriptive statistics were computed. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 22.0 was used for this purpose. In the following segment these are depicted briefly.

Table-1: Descriptive Statistics for Attitude towards Classroom Teaching

Attitude towards Classroom Teaching		N	Mean		Median	SD	Skewness		Kurtosis	
			Statistic	Std. Error			Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Total		382	148.7382	.54119	148.0000	10.57753	.163	.125	-.093	.249
Gender	Male	174	149.1264	.85032	148.0000	11.21653	.286	.184	-.213	.366
	Female	208	148.4135	.69529	148.0000	10.02760	-.004	.169	-.041	.366
Locale	Rural	211	148.7014	.71465	148.0000	10.38089	.284	.167	.184	.333
	Urban	171	148.7836	.82939	148.0000	10.84571	.033	.186	-.360	.369
Training	Trained	282	147.8723	.62667	147.0000	10.52356	.259	.145	.096	.289
	Untrained	100	151.1800	1.03966	151.0000	10.39656	-.089	.241	-.278	.478

The above table shows that, the total (N = 382) had mean score in Attitude towards Classroom Teaching is 148.7382, Median is 148.000, SD is 10.57753, Skewness is .163 and Kurtosis is -.093. The corresponding scores of these regarding the categorical variables namely gender, locale and training are also presented in that table.

RESULTS

For the purpose, the raw data were tabulated in MS Excel 2007 and analyses of data were done by the statistical software, IBM SPSS 22.0.

Table-2: Group Statistics for Attitude towards Classroom Teaching

	Variations	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
Attitude towards Classroom Teaching	Gender	Male	174	149.1264	11.21653	.85032
		Female	208	148.4135	10.02760	.69529
	Locale	Rural	211	148.7014	10.38089	.71465
		Urban	171	148.7836	10.84571	.82939
	Training	Trained	282	147.8723	10.52356	.62667
		Untrained	100	151.1800	10.39656	1.03966

Table-3: Independent Samples Test for Attitude towards Classroom Teaching

Attitude towards Classroom Teaching	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender (Male vs. Female)	Equal Variances Assumed	3.107	.079	.656 [#]	380	.512
Locale (Rural vs. Urban)	Equal Variances Assumed	.473	.492	-.075 [#]	380	.940
Training (Trained vs. Untrained)	Equal Variances Assumed	.018	.893	-2.709 [*]	380	.007

[#] Not significant at the 0.05 level

^{*} Significant at the 0.05 level

To test the homogeneity of variance, Levene's Test for Equality of Variance was considered. It showed that the F value of male and female was 3.107, rural and urban was .473 and trained and untrained was .018 and p value of those were .079, .492 and .893 respectively which were higher than 0.05, so the equal variances were assumed in the data. The table showed that t values were .656, .075 and 2.709 respectively, calculated for male & female, rural & urban and trained & untrained school teachers with df 380 and p values were .512 ($p > 0.05$), .940 ($p > 0.05$) and .007 ($p < 0.05$) respectively, hence the H_{01} and H_{02} were not rejected but H_{03} was rejected. Then it can be said that, there was no significant differences between male & female teachers and rural & urban teachers. But there was significant difference between trained & untrained teachers in their attitude towards classroom teaching.

DISCUSSION

The result showed no significant difference between male and female teachers and also between rural and urban school teachers in the present research but significant difference was there between trained and untrained school teachers. The implication of it can be said that both the

trained and untrained teachers were differed in many situations like; trying to establish participation with others and making friendship with others, accepting responsibility for one's success or failure, always interested to know from others as to how he/she has done, are attempting to excel someone and trying to show something unusual and training making efforts to reach for distant goals, thinking about making further advancement, fixing high standards for oneself and while facing difficulties to be interested in making one's best effort. On the other hand, both the male & female school teachers and rural & urban school teachers were of same opinions like; they are trying to be liked by others and indicating behavior like visiting to meet others, making arrangements for breakfast and food, attending clubs, accepting membership of institutions and parties etc., making effort to gain position and prestige and try to influence other person or group and they have strong desires for competing others, engaging one in such activities which generates conflicts, tensions or intense feeling, for example, to fall in discussion, to demand, to tell, to command, to punish others, controlling the flow of information and have the eagerness to know about one's influence on others, trying to get social appreciation to reach for distant goals, thinking about making further advancement, fixing high standards for oneself and while facing difficulties to be interested in making one's best effort.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study have many noteworthy educational implications that may be useful for different stakeholders of education like teachers, teacher educators, psychologists, educational planners, policy makers and schools. It is no exaggeration to utter that the whole educational process revolved round the teacher. Teacher plays an inevitable role not as a mere transmitter of knowledge and culture but as a changing agent also. It is the responsibility of the teacher to guide and inspire students, to inculcate societal bindings in consonance with our cultural heritage and educational objectives. The education system and especially teachers have very important roles in raising a healthy society and qualified individuals. The teacher has the power to influence all other variables about education. In order to be successful in teaching profession, one needs to love the profession and perform it willingly.

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